

From Exploration to Mastery: The Core of Reinforcement Learning

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ABSTRACT

The rapid progress of artificial intelligence (AI) has been fueled by the goal of creating autonomous systems that can make optimal decisions. In this pursuit, reinforcement learning (RL) has emerged as a powerful method for training such systems, as it enables the rewarding of desired behavior and facilitates decision-making processes. This report presents as an outcome of an independent study course conducted under the guidance of Professor Nguyen Van Dinh, with the aim of providing a comprehensive introduction to the field of RL.

The independent study course comprised weekly meetings, during which the student presented the knowledge acquired throughout the week. The course primarily drew upon the materials from the esteemed CS234 - Reinforcement Learning course offered by Stanford University [1], supplemented by the book “Reinforcement Learning: An Introduction” authored by Sutton and Barto [2]. The aforementioned resources served as the basis for delving into diverse problem types, algorithms, and fundamental challenges in the domain of Reinforcement Learning. The formulas and algorithms included in this report have been sourced from the above references. The course “Introduction to Reinforcement Learning with David Silver” [3] from DeepMind was also a great source of reference.

This report serves as a fundamental guide to RL, offering an in-depth exploration of the essential concepts and techniques necessary for understanding and effectively applying RL algorithms. It commences by introducing the basic principles of RL, encompassing topics such as Markov Decision Processes (MDPs) and Bellman equations. It delves into a range of RL algorithms, including Q-Learning, Monte Carlo Tree Search, policy gradient methods, and more, providing insights into their strengths and limitations. Furthermore, the report addresses critical challenges encountered in RL, such as the exploration-exploitation trade-off, function approximation, and generalization. Emphasis is placed on the significance of striking a balance between exploration and exploitation to discover optimal policies in dynamic environments. Additionally, it discusses methodologies for generalizing acquired knowledge to novel scenarios and explores the delicate balance between accuracy and efficiency in function approximation.

While this report primarily focuses on theoretical concepts, definitions, and potential use cases, it incorporates illustrative examples to enhance comprehension. Although it does not include practical exercises, code implementation, or hands-on projects, it leverages examples where necessary to elucidate concepts and ideas.

By providing a comprehensive overview of RL, this report equips readers with the foundational understanding required to define RL problems, implement algorithms, analyze performance, address exploration-exploitation challenges, and develop a solid understanding of RL fundamentals, paving the way for further exploration, research, and application in this dynamically evolving discipline. As the field of AI continues to progress, RL will play a pivotal role in the development of intelligent autonomous systems capable of making optimal decisions across diverse real-world applications.

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I. INTRODUCTION

A. About the topic

Reinforcement Learning (RL) is an interesting field of AI that focuses on constructing algorithms and models that enable agents to learn optimal decision-making strategies by interacting with their environment. RL is well-known for its ability to address complex problems that cannot be solved by conventional rules-based programming or supervised learning methods.

The importance of RL stems from its extensive application across several fields. Robotics, game play, recommendation systems, economics, healthcare, and a variety of other fields have found practical uses for RL. Its ability to adapt and learn through experiences gives RL agents the ability to deal with challenges that are complicated, unpredictable, and dynamic. RL agents develop their decision-making techniques to handle complex settings by constantly observing the state and analysing the effects of their actions.

The application of RL techniques contributes to the advancement of various domains, including robotics, game playing, recommendation systems, finance, and healthcare, among others. Its ability to learn from interactions and adapt to changing environments makes it suitable for problems with complex, uncertain, or dynamic characteristics.

B. The scope of the study

This report explores the foundational concepts, theories, and methodologies discussed during the course, including Markov decision processes, value functions, policy optimization, and exploration-exploitation trade-offs. Furthermore, the report delves into practical aspects of RL, such as function approximation and the integration of Deep Learning with RL.

C. The limitations of the study

Each strategy and method's strengths, flaws and practical implications are explored in this work. The report concentrates on providing a thorough knowledge of the fundamental ideas and methodologies presented, as well as their significance in RL research and applications. Because the report focuses more on the concepts and definitions, there will be few exercises and code implementations. There will be examples where necessary.

It is also worth noting that this paper is limited to the fundamentals of RL. While the study gives a detailed review of RL, significant developments and alternative methods in the area have lately discovered that may not be addressed. As a result, it is critical to consult other resources and remain current on the latest discoveries in RL.

II. BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

A. Background

As a branch of Machine Learning and AI, Reinforcement learning (RL) is inspired by behavioural psychology and tries to create intelligent agents capable of learning via interactions with their surroundings. RL is fundamentally based on the notion of an agent interacting with the environment around it. The agent acts in the environment and receives rewards or penalties based on the results of its actions as feedback. The RL agent aims to learn a policy function that maps the received states to actions that maximises the cumulative rewards earned over time. The RL agent learns to explore the environment, modify its choice of action through something called a policy, and optimise its decision-making approach through a process of exploration and exploitation. The process can simply described in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: A basic process in a Reinforcement Learning model

The learning paradigm of RL described above exhibits intriguing parallels with human cognition, as humans also acquire knowledge and skills through experience and interactions with their surroundings. Consequently, RL has been considered a field closely aligned with the concept of “Artificial Intelligence.” The ability of RL to learn from trial and error, simulating the learning processes observed in humans and animals, positions it as a powerful framework for training intelligent systems. Throughout the year, RL has seen tremendous developments and breakthroughs, owing to both theoretical and practical contributions. deep learning approaches, as well as the combination of deep neural networks with RL algorithms, have resulted in significant accomplishments in fields such as gaming, robotics, and natural language processing.

B. Objectives

This report aims to provide:

- **Comprehensive understanding:** To promote a thorough comprehension of the core concepts, theories, and approaches. This involves studying Markov decision processes, value functions, policy optimization, and exploration-exploitation trade-offs.
- **Systematic Content Presentation:** The report intends to facilitate a smooth and easy-to-follow knowledge of the concepts, methodologies, and applications covered by organising the study in a consistent and logical manner. This methodical organisation of information will allow readers to connect the various parts, guaranteeing a thorough understanding of the fundamental concepts of reinforcement learning.
- **Critical Evaluation:** This report reviews and analyses the methodologies and approaches' strengths, limitations, and practical consequences.
- **Practical Importance:** This report investigates the use of RL in a variety of sectors, including robotics, gaming, recommendation systems, finance, and healthcare, among others. Furthermore, the combination of deep learning and RL, as well as its practical consequences, will be addressed.
- **Resource for Researchers and Practitioners:** To function as a helpful resource for RL researchers, practitioners, and students, the report's goal is to provide insights, recommendations, and a thorough review of the fundamental concepts and approaches in RL. It will allow readers to gain a better knowledge of RL, investigate practical applications, and discover prospective research avenues.

III. MAIN CONTENT OF STUDY

A. Introduction to RL

1. Basic concepts of RL

Reinforcement Learning definition

Reinforcement Learning is a form of Machine Learning and AI that allows an agent to learn by observing the outcomes of actions in a specified environment. It involves an agent learns through repeated interactions with the environment, receives feedback and updates its policy to produce actions that maximizes the cumulative expected reward over time. The learning process of RL is driven by the principle of trial and error, where the agent does not know in advance how the world works and must learn from experience what brings good outcomes and what does not. As a result of the reward weak/incomplete feedback, we may consider Reinforcement Learning to be midway between Supervised Learning, which provides strong feedback with labelled data, and Unsupervised Learning, which provides no feedback or labels.

Reinforcement Learning involves:

- Optimization: The goal is to yield the best outcomes, or at least a very good strategy.
- Delayed consequences: Decisions made in a state can impact things many states later. This introduces two challenges: decisions involve reasoning about not just the immediate reward for a decision but also the long term return when planning; and assigning temporal credit is complex, for example, as it is hard to describe and understand if an action or element can cause high or low rewards in the long term when learning.
- Exploration: Reinforcement learning is often compared to an agent acting as a scientist, learning about the world by making decisions. The agent learns through trial and error, much like human. In RL, the agent only receives a reward for the decision it makes and has no information about the consequences of a different action. Decisions made in RL impact what the agent learns about the environment.
- Generalization: It is necessary that the agent can generalize from its past experiences to new situations that it has not encountered before. This is important because the agent will often encounter new situations that are similar but not identical to ones it has seen before. By generalizing from its past experiences, the agent can make better decisions in these new situations.

Basic components of a RL model

Figure 2: The Reinforcement Learning flow

Given the state s_t and reward R_t , action a_t is identified by having a policy $\pi(s)$ that maps the state observed to the action. The action, again impact the environment and receives feedback through the reward R_{t+1} . The policy will be updated by the estimating cummulative the reward and moving to the policy that outputs the action that yields the best return, which is the cummulative weighted reward of future states starting from t .

In general, RL models have the following components:

- State (usually denote as \mathbf{s}): A state represents the configuration or snapshot of the environment at a particular time. It captures key relevant information for the agent to make decisions. The state can be discrete or continuous.
- Action (usually denote as \mathbf{a}): Actions are the choices available to the agent at each step or in each state. The agent selects an action based on its current state and its learned policy. Actions can be discrete or continuous.
- Reward (denoted as $r(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a})$): A reward is a numerical feedback signal provided to the agent after it takes an action. The reward indicates the desirability or quality of a certain action that corresponds to the environment's goal.
- Policy (denoted as $\pi(\mathbf{a} | \mathbf{s})$): A policy represents the strategy or rule that the agent uses to identify its actions based on the current state. This function takes input state, outputs actions and guides the agent's decision-making process. The policy can be deterministic or stochastic, presenting the probability of selecting action \mathbf{a} given state \mathbf{s} .
- Transition Models (denoted as $T(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{s}')$ or $P(\mathbf{s}_i | \mathbf{s}_j)$): A model represents the agent's understanding or knowledge about the environment. It can be an optional component that provides the agent with the ability to predict or simulate the next state or reward based on the current state and action. The transition model captures the dynamics of the environment and store the information about the probability of going from one state to another when the corresponding action \mathbf{a} is taken.
- State Value Function (denoted as $V(\mathbf{s})$): This function estimates the expected cumulative reward an agent will receive from being in a given state and following a specific policy thereafter. It calculates the long-term value or optimality of being in a particular state. The state value function provides an estimate of the value of state \mathbf{s} under the agent's policy π .
- State-Action Value Function (denoted as $Q(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a})$): The state-action value function, also known as the Q-function, estimates the expected cumulative reward an agent will receive by taking action \mathbf{a} in a given state \mathbf{s} and following a specific policy thereafter. It represents the value or optimality of taking a particular action in a specific state. The state-action value function, provides an estimate of the value of the state-action pair (\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a}) under the agent's policy π .
- Constraints: Constraints refer to the limitations or conditions that need to be satisfied by the agent during its decision-making process. Constraints can be specified on actions, states, rewards, or other aspects of the RL problem and are typically denoted based on their specific context or formulation.

Markov Decision Process

Given the history is the information about the past states and actions performed, a system is Markov when the information state is considered sufficient statistics to represent the history. For example, the future decisions of a chess player only relies on the current setup of the chessboard and the position of the chess piece. The previous steps

that lead to the positions is not important. The optimal strategy for the next steps in the future is generated only from the current state of the chessboard only.

There are two main types of Markov Decision Process, which are the Markov Decision Process (MDP - Full Observability case) and the Partially Observable Markov Decision Process (POMDP - Partial Observability case). In the MDP case, the observed state and the world state is the same. The examples for this case can be the chessboard that we have mentioned above. In the POMDP case, the agent state is not the same as the world state. This POMDP can be seen in card games, where we only know the cards that we are currently having, and do not know exactly what set of cards other players are holding.

Model-based and Model-free problems

The key difference between model-based and model-free approaches in reinforcement learning lies in the presence or absence of an explicit model of the environment.

Model-Based:

- Model: Model-based approaches in RL involve the construction and utilization of an explicit model of the environment. This model captures the dynamics of the environment, including the transition probabilities between states and the rewards associated with state-action pairs.
- May or may not have policy and/or value function: In addition to the model, a model-based approach may also include a policy function and/or a value function. These components can be used to guide decision-making and evaluate the quality of states or actions.

Model-Free:

- Value function and/or policy function: In model-free approaches, the focus is on learning the value function and/or policy function directly from interacting with the environment. These functions are learned through trial and error, without explicitly building a model of the environment.
- No model: Unlike model-based approaches, model-free approaches do not rely on an explicit model that describes the environment's dynamics, such as transition probabilities or rewards. Instead, they learn directly from experiences gathered through interactions with the environment.

When referring to the type of sequential decision process, both cases of MDPs and POMDPs have actions that influence future observations, so credit assignments and strategic actions are really needed. Another type of sequential decision process are bandits, where actions have no influence on next observation. Bandit problems involve a single agent facing a set of arms or actions, where each action has an unknown reward distribution. The agent's goal is to learn the optimal action-selection strategy to maximize the total cumulative reward over a given time period. The agent does not have access to explicit state information or state transitions, and the focus is primarily on exploring different actions and exploiting the actions that appear to yield higher rewards. Bandit problems are typically simpler than other sequential decision processes like MDPs or POMDPs, as they do not involve explicit state transitions or the consid-

eration of long-term consequences. The emphasis in bandit problems is on exploring the available actions and learning their rewards through repeated trials, aiming to converge to the most rewarding action or arm. One example of bandits can be the advertisements showed for a customer does not effect the state and preferences of any other customer.

Deterministic and Stochastic

- **Deterministic:** A deterministic policy directly maps from state action, allowing for precise control and predictability in the agent's behavior. This is a common assumption in robotics and controls.
- **Stochastic:** In contrast, instead of always selecting a single action for a given state, a stochastic policy assigns probabilities to different actions, allowing for exploration of alternative actions and capturing uncertainty in the environment. The probabilities can be based on learned estimates or predefined distributions, enabling the agent to adapt its behavior and explore a broader range of actions by giving a distribution of actions might take. This is a common assumption in customer behavior, where a customer may like an advertisement or not, for example.

Exploration and Exploitation

- Exploration is the ability to do new things that may help the agent make better selections in the future.
- Exploitation is the ability to choose on actions that are likely to generate a positive return based on previous experience.

There often be a tradeoff between exploration and exploitation. The exploration-exploitation strategy is a mechanism that balances the exploration of new actions to gather more information about the environment and learn better policies, with the exploitation of already learned knowledge to maximize rewards. It determines how much the agent explores unknown actions versus exploiting known actions based on its current knowledge and uncertainty estimates.

On-Policy and Off-Policy

- On-policy learning is a type of reinforcement learning where the agent learns by following the same policy that it is estimating. In other words, the agent learns to estimate and evaluate a policy from experience obtained from following that policy. Direct experience is used to learn the optimal policy.
- Off-policy learning is another type of reinforcement learning where the agent learns to estimate and evaluate a policy using experience gathered from following a different policy. This means that the agent learns from experience that was generated by a different policy than the one it is currently estimating.

2. Model-based RL: Tabular MDP planning

Given a Model-based problem with transition model P . If the state space S are finite, the transition model can be an $S \times S$ matrix, with probability of going from one state to another is the component $P_{ij} = P(s_j|s_i)$, with i, j referring to the states of S . Horizon H is the number of finite steps in each episode. The return is given as G_t :

$$G_t = \sum_{i=t}^{H-1} \gamma_{i-t} r_i. \quad (1)$$

Where γ is the discount factor, $\gamma \in [0, 1]$ for representing an idea of normalized weight and ensure convergence.

- $\gamma = 0$: Only the immediate reward is important
- $\gamma = 1$: Future rewards and immediate reward are equally important

$\gamma = 1$ can be used for finite episode lengths. For infinite episode lengths, the convergence needs to be considered and choose the suitable γ . The state value function $V(s)$ is calculated as the expected value of the return at state s_t :

$$V(s_t) = E[G_t | s_t = s]. \quad (2)$$

Computing this value function of a Markov Reward Process: there are three common ways:

1. By simulation

Algorithm 1 Monte Carlo simulation to calculate MRP value function

```

1: procedure MONTE CARLO EVALUATION( $M, s, t, N$ )
2:    $i \leftarrow 0$ 
3:    $G_t \leftarrow 0$ 
4:   while  $i \neq N$  do
5:     Generate an episode, starting from state  $s$  and time  $t$ 
6:     Using the generated episode, calculate return  $g \leftarrow \sum_{i=t}^{H-1} \gamma^{i-t} r_i$ 
7:      $G_t \leftarrow G_t + g$ 
8:      $i \leftarrow i + 1$ 
9:    $V_t(s) \leftarrow G_t / N$ 
10:  return  $V_t(s)$ 

```

2. By analytic solution

For finite Markov Reward Process, $V(s)$ can be expressed as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} V(s_1) \\ V(s_2) \\ \vdots \\ V(s_N) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} R(s_1) \\ R(s_2) \\ \vdots \\ R(s_N) \end{pmatrix} + \gamma \begin{pmatrix} P(s_1|s_1) & P(s_2|s_1) & \dots & P(s_N|s_1) \\ P(s_1|s_2) & P(s_2|s_2) & \dots & P(s_N|s_2) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ P(s_1|s_N) & P(s_2|s_N) & \dots & P(s_N|s_N) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} V(s_1) \\ V(s_2) \\ \vdots \\ V(s_N) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

from that we obtain:

$$V = (I - \gamma P)^{-1} R. \quad (4)$$

Where $(I - \gamma P)$ is invertible.

3. By iterative algorithm

Using dynamic programming, for input finite horizon MRP $M = (S, P, R, \gamma)$:

Algorithm 2 Dynamic programming algorithm to calculate finite MRP value function

```

1: procedure DYNAMIC PROGRAMMING VALUE FUNCTION EVALUATION( $M$ )
2:   For all states  $s \in S$ ,  $V_H(s) \leftarrow 0$ 
3:    $t \leftarrow H - 1$ 
4:   while  $t \geq 0$  do
5:     For all states  $s \in S$ ,  $V_t(s) = R(s) + \gamma \sum_{s' \in S} P(s'|s)V_{t+1}(s')$ 
6:      $t \leftarrow t - 1$ 
7:   return  $V_t(s)$  for all  $s \in S$  and  $t = 0, \dots, H$ 

```

Using iterative algorithm, for infinite case with $\gamma < 1$, take input $M = (S, P, R, \gamma)$:

Algorithm 3 Iterative algorithm to calculate MRP value function

```

1: procedure ITERATIVE VALUE FUNCTION EVALUATION( $M, \epsilon$ )
2:   For all states  $s \in S$ ,  $V'(s) \leftarrow 0$ ,  $V(s) \leftarrow \infty$ 
3:   while  $\|V - V'\|_\infty > \epsilon$  do
4:      $V \leftarrow V'$ 
5:     For all states  $s \in S$ ,  $V'(s) = R(s) + \gamma \sum_{s' \in S} P(s'|s)V(s')$ 
6:   return  $V'(s)$  for all  $s \in S$ 

```

Bellman operator:

For policy evaluation, Bellman operator is an important concept. The Bellman equation describes the link between the value function of one state (state-action), its expected immediate reward and the value function of the next state (state-action). The Bellman operator is used to modify the value function until it converges to the optimal value that satisfies the Bellman optimality equation.

Repeatedly applying the Bellman operator, RL algorithms can find an optimal policy that maximizes the expected sum of reward in an environment, as a policy evaluation process:

- Initialize $V_0(s) = 0$ for all s
- For $k = 1$ until convergence, for all s in S :

$$V_k^\pi(s) = r(s, \pi(s)) + \gamma \sum_{s' \in S} p(s'|s, \pi(s))V_{k-1}^\pi(s'). \quad (5)$$

The Bellman operator contracts the value closer to the optimal value. This ensures the idea of monotonic improvement, where the updated state value function is larger or equal to the previous state value function.

Policy evaluation

Policy evaluation is a fundamental step in reinforcement learning algorithms, where the value function of each state (state-action) under a given policy is estimated. In the infinite horizon case, with:

- $\gamma < 1$, stationary policy π , tolerance ϵ
- Input a Markov decision process $M = (S, A, P, R, \gamma)$
- Output value function of all states.

The procedure is as below:

Algorithm 4 Iterative algorithm to calculate MDP value function for a stationary policy π

```
1: procedure POLICY EVALUATION( $M, \pi, \epsilon$ )
2:   For all states  $s \in S$ , define  $R^\pi(s) = \sum_{a \in A} \pi(a|s)R(s, a)$ 
3:   For all states  $s, s' \in S$ , define  $P^\pi(s'|s) = \sum_{a \in A} \pi(a|s)P(s'|s, a)$ 
4:   For all states  $s \in S$ ,  $V'(s) \leftarrow 0$ ,  $V(s) \leftarrow \infty$ 
5:   while  $\|V - V'\|_\infty > \epsilon$  do
6:      $V \leftarrow V'$ 
7:     For all states  $s \in S$ ,  $V'(s) = R^\pi(s) + \gamma \sum_{s' \in S} P^\pi(s'|s)V(s')$ 
8:   return  $V'(s)$  for all  $s \in S$ 
```

Policy search

- Input MDP $M = (S, A, P, R, \gamma)$ and a tolerance ϵ for accuracy of policy evaluation
- Output: optimal value function and optimal policy

The procedure is as follows:

Algorithm 5 Policy search algorithm to calculate optimal value function and find an optimal policy

```
1: procedure POLICY SEARCH( $M, \epsilon$ )
2:    $\Pi \leftarrow$  All stationary deterministic policies of  $M$ 
3:    $\pi^* \leftarrow$  Randomly choose a policy  $\pi \in \Pi$ 
4:    $V^* \leftarrow$  POLICY EVALUATION ( $M, \pi^*, \epsilon$ )
5:   for  $\pi \in \Pi$  do
6:      $V^\pi \leftarrow$  POLICY EVALUATION ( $M, \pi, \epsilon$ )
7:     if  $V^\pi(s) \geq V^*(s)$  for all  $s \in S$ , then
8:        $V^* \leftarrow V^\pi$ 
9:        $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ 
10:  return  $V^*(s), \pi^*(s)$  for all  $s \in S$ 
```

Policy iteration

We know that given a policy π , there exists a policy that is at least equal or better than the existing one. As a result, we can find the improved policy as follows:

Algorithm 6 Policy improvement algorithm to improve an input policy

```
1: procedure POLICY IMPROVEMENT( $M, V^\pi$ )
2:    $\hat{\pi}(s) \leftarrow \arg \max_{a \in A} [R(s, a) + \gamma \sum_{s' \in S} P(s'|s, a)V^\pi(s')]$  ,  $\forall s \in S$ 
3:   return  $\hat{\pi}(s)$  for all  $s \in S$ 
```

With the improved policy, performing this method iteratively can move the policy towards optimal point. The policy iteration can be performed as follows:

Algorithm 7 Policy iteration algorithm to calculate optimal value function and find an optimal policy

```

1: procedure POLICY ITERATION( $M, \epsilon$ )
2:    $\pi \leftarrow$  Randomly choose a policy  $\pi \in \Pi$ 
3:   while true do
4:      $V^\pi \leftarrow$  POLICY EVALUATION ( $M, \pi, \epsilon$ )
5:      $\pi^* \leftarrow$  POLICY IMPROVEMENT ( $M, V^\pi$ )
6:     if  $\pi^*(s) = \pi(s)$  then
7:       break
8:     else
9:        $\pi \leftarrow \pi^*$ 
10:   $V^* \leftarrow V^\pi$ 
11:  return  $V^*(s), \pi^*(s)$  for all  $s \in S$ 

```

Value iteration

Value iteration is another technique that finds the optimal value function and policy. This is an iterative algorithm that updates the value function of each state in the MDP until convergence to the optimal values.

- Input: horizon MDP $M = (S, A, P, R, \gamma)$, tolerance ϵ
- Output: optimal value function, optimal policy

The procedure can be described as follows:

- For infinite horizon:

Algorithm 8 Value iteration algorithm to calculate optimal value function and find an optimal policy

```

1: procedure VALUE ITERATION( $M, \epsilon$ )
2:   For all states  $s \in S, V'(s) \leftarrow 0, V(s) \leftarrow \infty$ 
3:   while  $\|V - V'\|_\infty > \epsilon$  do
4:      $V \leftarrow V'$ 
5:     For all states  $s \in S, V'(s) = \max_{a \in A} [R(s, a) + \gamma \sum_{s' \in S} P(s'|s, a)V(s')]$ 
6:      $V^* \leftarrow V$  for all  $s \in S$ 
7:      $\pi^* \leftarrow \arg \max_{a \in A} [R(s, a) + \gamma \sum_{s' \in S} P(s'|s, a)V^*(s')] , \forall s \in S$ 
8:     return  $V^*(s), \pi^*(s)$  for all  $s \in S$ 

```

- For finite horizon:

Algorithm 9 Value iteration algorithm for finite horizon MDPs

```

1: procedure FINITE VALUE ITERATION( $M$ )
2:   For all states  $s \in S, V_H^*(s) \leftarrow 0$ 
3:    $t \leftarrow H - 1$ 
4:   while  $t \geq 0$  do
5:     For all states  $s \in S, V_t^*(s) = \max_{a \in A} [R(s, a) + \gamma \sum_{s' \in S} P(s'|s, a)V_{t+1}^*(s')]$ 
6:     For all states  $s \in S, \pi_t^* = \arg \max_{a \in A} [R(s, a) + \gamma \sum_{s' \in S} P(s'|s, a)V_{t+1}^*(s')]$ 
7:      $t \leftarrow t - 1$ 
8:   return For all states  $s \in S, V_t^*(s)$  for  $t = 0, \dots, H, \pi_t^*(s)$  for  $t = 0, \dots, H - 1$ 

```

3. Model-free RL: Policy Evaluation Recall: Dynamic Programming for Model-Based Policy Evaluation

Recall from the previous part, dynamic programming computes the state value function by adding the reward of the current state and bootstrapping the rest of the return. The algorithm can be found in Algorithm 2 & 3, part III.A.2. For convenience, the algorithm is described simply as below:

Algorithm 1 Iterative algorithm to calculate MDP value function for a stationary policy π

```

1: procedure POLICY EVALUATION( $M, \pi, \epsilon$ )
2:   For all states  $s \in S$ , define  $R^\pi(s) = \sum_{a \in A} \pi(a|s)R(s, a)$ 
3:   For all states  $s, s' \in S$ , define  $P^\pi(s'|s) = \sum_{a \in A} \pi(a|s)P(s'|s, a)$ 
4:   For all states  $s \in S$ ,  $V_0(s) \leftarrow 0$ 
5:    $k \leftarrow 0$ 
6:   while  $k = 0$  or  $\|V_k - V_{k-1}\|_\infty > \epsilon$  do
7:      $k \leftarrow k + 1$ 
8:     For all states  $s \in S$ ,  $V_k(s) = R^\pi(s) + \gamma \sum_{s' \in S} P^\pi(s'|s)V_{k-1}(s')$ 
9:   return  $V_k$ 

```

The structure and idea of bootstrapping can be visually described as below:

Figure 3: The idea of bootstrapping, using the value estimate V_{k-1}

Monte Carlo On Policy Evaluation

Monte Carlo is a very popular model-free computational method. The idea of this method is very simple. Execute many episodes under policy π until termination and record the returns G_t starting at state s . With the sample, take an average of the return to estimate $V_\pi(s)$.

The two forms of Monte Carlo on policy evaluation are differentiated by whether we take an average over just the first time we visit a state in each rollout or every time we visit the state in each rollout. The former is called First-Visit Monte Carlo On Policy Evaluation while the latter is called Every-Visit Monte Carlo On Policy Evaluation.

- For First-visit:

Algorithm 2 First-Visit Monte Carlo Policy Evaluation

```

1: procedure FIRST-VISIT-MONTE-CARLO( $h_1, \dots, h_j$ )
2:   For all states  $s$ ,  $N(s) \leftarrow 0$ ,  $S(s) \leftarrow 0$ ,  $V(s) \leftarrow 0$ 
3:   for each episode  $h_j$  do
4:     for  $t = 1, \dots, L_j$  do
5:       if  $s_{j,t} \neq s_{j,u}$  for  $u < t$  then
6:          $N(s_{j,t}) \leftarrow N(s_{j,t}) + 1$ 
7:          $S(s_{j,t}) \leftarrow S(s_{j,t}) + G_{j,t}$ 
8:          $V^\pi(s_{j,t}) \leftarrow S(s_{j,t})/N(s_{j,t})$ 
9:   return  $V^\pi$ 

```

- For Every-visit:

Algorithm 3 Every-Visit Monte Carlo Policy Evaluation

```

1: procedure EVERY-VISIT-MONTE-CARLO( $h_1, \dots, h_j$ )
2:   For all states  $s$ ,  $N(s) \leftarrow 0$ ,  $S(s) \leftarrow 0$ ,  $V(s) \leftarrow 0$ 
3:   for each episode  $h_j$  do
4:     for  $t = 1, \dots, L_j$  do
5:        $N(s_{j,t}) \leftarrow N(s_{j,t}) + 1$ 
6:        $S(s_{j,t}) \leftarrow S(s_{j,t}) + G_{j,t}$ 
7:        $V^\pi(s_{j,t}) \leftarrow S(s_{j,t})/N(s_{j,t})$ 
8:   return  $V^\pi$ 

```

Instead of updating using the state S , we can update the value function with the idea of the new average value is the sum of $N(s_{j,t}) - 1$ old values $V^\pi(s_{j,t})$ divide by the new return $G_{j,t}$. The new update step is as follows:

$$V^\pi(s_{j,t}) \leftarrow \frac{V^\pi(s_{j,t}) \times (N(s_{j,t}) - 1) + G_{j,t}}{N(s_{j,t})} = V^\pi(s_{j,t}) + \frac{1}{N(s_{j,t})} (G_{j,t} - V^\pi(s_{j,t})) \quad (6)$$

We have the incremental form for Monte Carlo:

- For First-visit:

Algorithm 4 Incremental First-Visit Monte Carlo Policy Evaluation

```

1: procedure INCREMENTAL-FIRST-VISIT-MONTE-CARLO( $\alpha, h_1, \dots, h_j$ )
2:   For all states  $s$ ,  $N(s) \leftarrow 0$ ,  $V(s) \leftarrow 0$ 
3:   for each episode  $h_j$  do
4:     for  $t = 1, \dots, terminal$  do
5:       if  $s_{j,t} \neq s_{j,u}$  for  $u < t$  then
6:          $N(s_{j,t}) \leftarrow N(s_{j,t}) + 1$ 
7:          $V^\pi(s_{j,t}) \leftarrow V^\pi(s) + \alpha(G_{j,t} - V^\pi(s))$ 
8:   return  $V^\pi$ 

```

- For Every-visit:

Algorithm 5 Incremental Every-Visit Monte Carlo Policy Evaluation

```

1: procedure INCREMENTAL-EVERY-VISIT-MONTE-CARLO( $\alpha, h_1, \dots, h_j$ )
2:   For all states  $s$ ,  $N(s) \leftarrow 0$ ,  $V(s) \leftarrow 0$ 
3:   for each episode  $h_j$  do
4:     for  $t = 1, \dots, \text{terminal}$  do
5:        $N(s_{j,t}) \leftarrow N(s_{j,t}) + 1$ 
6:        $V^\pi(s_{j,t}) \leftarrow V^\pi(s) + \alpha(G_{j,t} - V^\pi(s))$ 
7:   return  $V^\pi$ 
  
```

With $\alpha = \frac{1}{N(s_{j,t})}$, we obtain the same algorithms as Algorithms 2 and 3 above in the original form.

With $\alpha > \frac{1}{N(s_{j,t})}$, higher weight is given in non-stationary domains by giving more favor to newer data.

Temporal Difference (TD) Learning

This is another method for model-free problems that combines bootstrapping of dynamic programming with sampling from Monte Carlo. Instead of waiting for the episode to terminate like in Monte Carlo, apply bootstrapping, replace G_t with the estimate $r_t + \gamma V_\pi(s_{t+1})$. The diagram as follows:

Figure 4: The diagram of the bootstrapping process to replace G_t

The detailed pseudo-code is as follows:

Algorithm 6 TD Learning to evaluate policy π

```
1: procedure TDLEARNING(step size  $\alpha$ , number of trajectories  $n$ )
2:   For all states  $s$ ,  $V^\pi(s) \leftarrow 0$ 
3:   while  $n > 0$  do
4:     Begin episode  $E$  at state  $s$ 
5:     while  $n > 0$  and episode  $E$  has not terminated do
6:        $a \leftarrow$  action at state  $s$  under policy  $\pi$ 
7:       Take action  $a$  in  $E$  and observe reward  $r$ , next state  $s'$ 
8:        $V^\pi(s) \leftarrow V^\pi(s) + \alpha(R + \gamma V^\pi(s') - V^\pi(s))$ 
9:        $s \leftarrow s'$ 
10:  return  $V^\pi$ 
```

Summarize the strengths and weaknesses of the methods

These methods all converges to the true value. The strengths and weaknesses of the three methods discussed above can be summarized as follows:

Dynamic Programming:

Strengths:

- Model-based problems only
- Applicable for non-episodic domains

Weaknesses:

- Not applicable for non-Markovian domains

Monte Carlo:

Strengths:

- Applicable for model-free problems
- Applicable for non-Markovian domains
- Unbiased estimate

Weaknesses:

- Not applicable for non-episodic domains
- High variance

Temporal Difference

Strengths:

- Applicable for model-free problems
- Applicable for non-episodic domains
- Low variance

Weaknesses:

- Not applicable for non-Markovian domains
- Biased estimate

4. Q-Learning - Model-free control

ϵ -greedy policies

The exploration strategy of ϵ -greedy engage in a random action with a low probability and then engage in greedy behaviour the rest of the time.

$$\pi(a|s) = \begin{cases} a & \text{with probability } \frac{\epsilon}{|A|} \\ \arg \max_a Q^\pi(s, a) & \text{with probability } 1 - \epsilon. \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Greedy in the Limit of Infinite Exploration (GLIE) policy: each and every state-action pair is visited for an infinite number of times, and the policy is greedy at the limit. With values such as $\epsilon_i = \frac{1}{i}$, the GLIE is satisfied. Also, it can be proved that a policy improve monotonically if we act ϵ -greedy on the current ϵ -greedy policy. This is a method that has monotonic improvement.

Monte Carlo Control with ϵ -greedy exploration strategy

Combining the ϵ -greedy strategy at the policy with the Monte Carlo method in the previous part, we obtain a Monte Carlo online control algorithm. For first-visit online Monte Carlo control, the procedure is as follows:

Algorithm 1 Online Monte Carlo Control/On Policy Improvement

```
1: procedure ONLINE MONTE CARLO CONTROL
2:   Initialize  $Q(s, a) = 0$ ,  $Returns(s, a) = 0$  for all  $s \in S, a \in A$ 
3:   Set  $\epsilon \leftarrow 1$ ,  $k \leftarrow 1$ 
4:   loop
5:     Sample  $k$ th episode  $(s_{k1}, a_{k1}, r_{k1}, s_{k2}, \dots, s_T)$  under policy  $\pi$ 
6:     for  $t = 1, \dots, T$  do
7:       if First visit to  $(s, a)$  in episode  $k$  then
8:         Append  $\sum_{j=t}^T r_{kj}$  to  $Returns(s_t, a_t)$ 
9:          $Q(s_t, a_t) \leftarrow average(Returns(s_t, a_t))$ 
10:     $k \leftarrow k + 1$ ,  $\epsilon = \frac{1}{k}$ 
11:     $\pi_k = \epsilon$ -greedy with respect to  $Q$  (policy improvement)
12:  Return  $Q, \pi$ 
```

The algorithm converges with the condition of GLIE mentioned above.

SARSA - On-policy method of Temporal Difference with ϵ -greedy strategy

Having similar idea, the on-policy method of TD Learning combines Temporal Difference with the exploration strategy. The name SARSA - State Action Reward State Action comes from the fact that we need those information to update Q , as written in the procedure below:

Algorithm 2 SARSA

```
1: procedure SARSA( $\epsilon, \alpha_t$ )
2:   Initialize  $Q(s, a)$  for all  $s \in S, a \in A$  arbitrarily except  $Q(\text{terminal}, \cdot) = 0$ 
3:    $\pi \leftarrow \epsilon$ -greedy policy with respect to  $Q$ 
4:   for each episode do
5:     Set  $s_1$  as the starting state
6:     Choose action  $a_1$  from policy  $\pi(s_1)$ 
7:     loop until episode terminates
8:       Take action  $a_t$  and observe reward  $r_t$  and next state  $s_{t+1}$ 
9:       Choose action  $a_{t+1}$  from policy  $\pi(s_{t+1})$ 
10:       $Q(s_t, a_t) \leftarrow Q(s_t, a_t) + \alpha_t[r_t + \gamma Q(s_{t+1}, a_{t+1}) - Q(s_t, a_t)]$ 
11:       $\pi \leftarrow \epsilon$ -greedy with respect to  $Q$  (policy improvement)
12:       $t \leftarrow t + 1$ 
13:   Return  $Q, \pi$ 
```

The algorithm converges to optimal with the condition of GLIE and the step size a_t between 0 to less than 1.

Q - Learning - Off-policy method of Temporal Difference with ϵ -greedy

The key idea of this method is take state-action Q estimates and bootstrap best future actions value function estimates. Q-learning is an off-policy algorithm because it takes the maximum over the actions at the next state, which means that the action it chooses is not necessarily the same as the one it would derive from the current policy. In other words, Q-learning learns by estimating the optimal policy using information collected from following another policy. The detailed pseudo-code is as follows:

Algorithm 3 Q-Learning with ϵ -greedy exploration

```
1: procedure Q-LEARNING( $\epsilon, \alpha, \gamma$ )
2:   Initialize  $Q(s, a)$  for all  $s \in S, a \in A$  arbitrarily except  $Q(\text{terminal}, \cdot) = 0$ 
3:    $\pi \leftarrow \epsilon$ -greedy policy with respect to  $Q$ 
4:   for each episode do
5:     Set  $s_1$  as the starting state
6:      $t \leftarrow 1$ 
7:     loop until episode terminates
8:       Sample action  $a_t$  from policy  $\pi(s_t)$ 
9:       Take action  $a_t$  and observe reward  $r_t$  and next state  $s_{t+1}$ 
10:       $Q(s_t, a_t) \leftarrow Q(s_t, a_t) + \alpha(r_t + \gamma \max_{a'} Q(s_{t+1}, a') - Q(s_t, a_t))$ 
11:       $\pi \leftarrow \epsilon$ -greedy policy with respect to  $Q$  (policy improvement)
12:       $t \leftarrow t + 1$ 
13:   return  $Q, \pi$ 
```

The conditions of convergence is the algorithm is GLIE and the step size a_t between 0 to less than 1.

SARSA and Q-Learning: Which one is preferred?

SARSA only perform better at some cases where negative outcomes come early on since it is realistic. Other than that, Q Learning is preferred. Optimistic is very important in exploration.

The optimistic aspect of exploration is also important in reinforcement learning. It encourages the agent to explore unfamiliar states and actions by initializing the Q-values optimistically. Q-Learning, being an off-policy algorithm, is more suited to optimistic

exploration. By using an ϵ -greedy strategy, it can explore different actions even when the Q-values are initially optimistic. SARSA's on-policy updates make it more conservative in exploration, as it is directly influenced by the current policy.

Double Q-Learning

The main idea of Double Q-Learning is having two independent unbiased estimates, Q_1 and Q_2 . One of them is used to make decisions by selecting the maximum, the other to estimate the value of this maximum.

Algorithm 4 Double Q-Learning

```

1: procedure DOUBLE Q-LEARNING( $\epsilon, \alpha, \gamma$ )
2:   Initialize  $Q_1(s, a), Q_2(s, a)$  for all  $s \in S, a \in A$ , set  $t \leftarrow 0$ 
3:    $\pi \leftarrow \epsilon$ -greedy policy with respect to  $Q_1 + Q_2$ 
4:   loop
5:     Sample action  $a_t$  from policy  $\pi$  at state  $s_t$ 
6:     Take action  $a_t$  and observe reward  $r_t$  and next state  $s_{t+1}$ 
7:     if (with 0.5 probability) then
8:        $Q_1(s_t, a_t) \leftarrow Q_1(s_t, a_t) + \alpha(r_t + \gamma Q_2(s_{t+1}, \arg \max_{a'} Q_1(s_{t+1}, a')) - Q_1(s_t, a_t))$ 
9:     else
10:       $Q_2(s_t, a_t) \leftarrow Q_2(s_t, a_t) + \alpha(r_t + \gamma Q_1(s_{t+1}, \arg \max_{a'} Q_2(s_{t+1}, a')) - Q_2(s_t, a_t))$ 
11:     $\pi \leftarrow \epsilon$ -greedy policy with respect to  $Q_1 + Q_2$  (policy improvement)
12:     $t \leftarrow t + 1$ 
13:  return  $\pi, Q_1 + Q_2$ 

```

This method significantly speeds up training time and eliminate suboptimal actions more quickly comparing to Q-Learning.

B. Function approximation

In order to make decisions and learn to make decisions, we have to be able to generalize from our prior experience so that even when end up in a state action pair that we have not encountered exactly before, we are still able to make good decisions.

With generalization, the benefits are:

- Reduce the memory needed to store
- Reduce computation needed to compute
- Reduce experience (data) needed to find a good policy

Amongst all of the function approximators, such as Neural Networks, Linear combination of features, Nearest Neighbors, Decision Trees, function approximators that are differentiable have the most attention, since they are smooth optimization properties, which means they are easier to optimize for. However, they are not always the right choice. For example, decision trees are very good for highly interpretation cases.

This report will focus mostly on linear value function approximation and neural networks, which are two approximators that are differentiable.

1. Linear value function approximation

To simply put it, we aim to approximate the value function by the linear combination of the feature vectors. For example, a robot has 360 sensors that expand around it to measure the distance between it and the obstacles around the robot. We will have a feature vector of size 360, each component in the vector records the distance.

We use a feature vector to represent the states:

$$x(s) = [x_1(s), x_2(s), \dots, x_n(s)]. \quad (8)$$

From the feature vector, we can construct an approximation of the value function using the linear combination:

$$\hat{v}(s, w) = x(s)^T w = \sum_{j=1}^n x_{j(s)} w_j \quad (9)$$

where w is the weight vector (also denoted as \mathbf{w} in algorithms).

From the approximation, a loss function (objective function) can be constructed as:

$$J(w) = \mathbb{E}_\pi [(v_\pi(s) - \hat{v}(s, w))^2]. \quad (10)$$

In order for our approximation to best fit the true value, the goal is to minimize this loss function.

Gradient descent and stochastic gradient descent

In order to minimize the value of the above function, a common technique is gradient descent. The gradient of the loss function is computed, with corresponding weight w . Then, we take steps along the negative direction of the gradient vector to minimize the objective function and update until we reach convergence criteria. This can simply be understood as taking steps towards the optimal point.

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_w J(w) &= \left[\frac{\partial J(w)}{\partial w_1}, \frac{\partial J(w)}{\partial w_2}, \dots, \frac{\partial J(w)}{\partial w_n} \right] \\ \nabla w &= -\frac{1}{2} \alpha \nabla_w J(w) \\ w &\leftarrow w + \nabla w. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

In many cases, stochastic gradient descent is used much more frequently due to data efficiency. Instead of considering everything, stochastic gradient descent does gradient descent on smaller sample. It is expected that the stochastic gradient descent is the same as doing gradient update on the full dataset.

Monte Carlo with linear function approximation

Simply replace the value function with the approximation, and generate value of returns by running many episodes with Monte Carlo, we obtain the Monte Carlo with linear function approximation:

Algorithm 1 Monte Carlo Linear Value Function Approximation for Policy Evaluation

```
1: Initialize  $\mathbf{w} = 0$ ,  $Return(s) = 0 \forall s$ ,  $k = 1$ 
2: loop
3:   Sample k-th episode  $(s_{k1}, a_{k1}, r_{k1}, s_{k2}, \dots, s_k, L_k)$  given  $\pi$ 
4:   for  $t = 1, \dots, L_k$  do
5:     if first visit to  $(s)$  in episode  $k$  then
6:       Append  $\sum_{j=t}^{L_k} r_{kj}$  to  $Return(s_t)$ 
7:        $\mathbf{w} \leftarrow \mathbf{w} + \alpha(Return(s_t) - \hat{v}(s_t, \mathbf{w}))x(s_t)$ 
8:    $k = k + 1$ 
```

Although this is an unbiased estimate, it is very noisy due to the nature of the Monte Carlo method.

Temporal Difference (TD(0)) with linear function approximation

Similarly, from the tabular setting of Temporal Difference given above, the only modification here is the update function. Now, the update function is:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{V}^\pi(s, w) &= \hat{V}^\pi(s, w) + \alpha(r + \gamma \hat{V}^\pi(s', w) - \hat{V}^\pi(s, w)) \nabla_w \hat{V}^\pi(s, w) \\ &= \hat{V}^\pi(s, w) + \alpha(r + \gamma \hat{V}^\pi(s', w) - \hat{V}^\pi(s, w)) x(s).\end{aligned}\tag{12}$$

Although this is a biased estimate, the true value will still converge to global optimum.

Q-Learning in linear function approximation

Although the method to intergrate linear function approximation in Q-Learning is quite similar to the methods above, it is very unstable. Combining function approximation, bootstrapping and off-policy learning, the model may fail to converge.

Summarize the convergence of control methods

The convergence guarantees of the three methods discussed above can be summarized as follows:

Monte-Carlo Control:

- Converge to optimal value for tabular case
- Converge to around near optimal value for linear value function approximation
- Does not guarantee to converge for nonlinear value function approximation

SARSA:

- Converge to optimal value for tabular case
- Converge to around near optimal value for linear value function approximation
- Does not guarantee to converge for nonlinear value function approximation

Q-learning:

- Converge to optimal value for tabular case
- Does not guarantee to converge for linear value function approximation
- Does not guarantee to converge for nonlinear value function approximation

2. CNNs and Deep Q-Learning

The performance of linear function approximators is heavily dependent on feature quality. Also, handcrafting an acceptable collection of characteristics can be challenging and time-consuming in general. To solve the above problems, deep learning is thought of as a solution. Deep neural networks (DNNs) can be used as function approximators which can increase the generalization ability even more.

The procedure of Deep Q-Learning (also known as DeepRL) is as follows:

Algorithm 1 deep Q-learning

- 1: Initialize replay memory D with a fixed capacity
 - 2: Initialize action-value function \hat{q} with random weights \mathbf{w}
 - 3: Initialize target action-value function \hat{q}^- with weights $\mathbf{w}^- = \mathbf{w}$
 - 4: **for** episode $m = 1, \dots, M$ **do**
 - 5: Observe initial frame x_1 and preprocess frame to get state s_1
 - 6: **for** time step $t = 1, \dots, T$ **do**
 - 7: Select action $a_t = \begin{cases} \text{random action} & \text{with probability } \epsilon \\ \arg \max_a \hat{q}(s_t, a, \mathbf{w}) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$
 - 8: Execute action a_t in emulator and observe reward r_t and image x_{t+1}
 - 9: Preprocess s_t, x_{t+1} to get s_{t+1} , and store transition (s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1}) in D
 - 10: Sample uniformly a random minibatch of N transitions (s_j, a_j, r_j, s_{j+1}) from D
 - 11: Set $y_j = r_j$ if episode ends at step $j + 1$;
 - 12: otherwise set $y_j = r_j + \gamma \max_{a'} \hat{q}(s_{j+1}, a', \mathbf{w}^-)$
 - 13: Perform a stochastic gradient descent step on $J(\mathbf{w}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N (y_j - \hat{q}(s_j, a_j, \mathbf{w}))^2$ w.r.t. parameters \mathbf{w}
 - 14: Every C steps reset $\mathbf{w}^- = \mathbf{w}$
-

For example, as an input state is a frame from a game, the use of convolutional neural network (CNNs) to approximate the function. The network takes preprocessed pixel image as inputs, and outputs a vector with value functions for actions as components. Each component corresponds to an action, denoted as \hat{q} .

The objective function of Deep Q Network (DQN) is:

$$J(w) = \mathbb{E}_{(s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1})} \left[\left(y_t^{DQN} - \hat{q}(s_t, a_t, w) \right)^2 \right]. \quad (13)$$

where y_t^{DQN} is the one step ahead learning target:

$$y_t^{DQN} = r_t + \gamma \max_{a'} \hat{q}(s_{t+1}, a', w^-). \quad (14)$$

When trying to do supervised learning, training the function value predictor, we do not always have the true value V_π . Instead, Q-learning constantly estimate and update policy. Each constantly changing for each step. Therefore, Deep Q Network introduces two new changes to make the model more stable:

- Experience replay: To remove correlations, a dataset D stores prior experience in the tuple format (s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1}) . To perform experience replay, we sample tuples like above and store in D . Next, calculate the target value from the sampled tuples:

$$r + \gamma \max_{a'} \hat{Q}(s', a', w). \quad (15)$$

Then, gradient descent can be used to update the network weights.

- Fixed-Q targets: A separate target network $\hat{q}(s, a, w^-)$ is updated every C updates/steps by duplicating the data of the parameters ($w^- = w$) from the online network $\hat{q}(s, a, w)$. The target network stays unaltered and creates y_j targets for the subsequent C updates.

3. A few other methods

This part considers the problems that we already have knowledge on, and explore how to immitate and learn from expert behavior from human. In scenarios where data gathering is slow, hard to obtain, or failure must be avoided, and safety must be ensured.

Immitation Learning

The process of the agent learn how to immitate the expert trajectories given. The expert perform some expert trajectories in the form of state-action sequences. The detailed process can be described as:

- Demonstration Collection: Expert demonstrations are recorded. Each demonstration consists of states and the corresponding actions taken by the expert.
- Training a Policy: A machine learning algorithm is used to train a policy network or model based on the collected dataset. The method aims to learn a state-action mapping that mimics the expert behavior.
- Evaluation and Refinement: The trained policy is evaluated on a separate validation set or by deploying it in the task environment.

Behavioral cloning

Given data tuples, the aim is to use supervised learning to map states to corresponding actions that belongs to the same tuple.

In the DAGGER algorithm, to mitigate the problem of compounding errors by adding data for newly visited states, we assume that we can generate more data from an expert instead of assuming there is a predefined set of expert demonstrations. The algorithm is as follows:

Algorithm 1 DAGGER

- 1: Initialize $\mathcal{D} \leftarrow \emptyset$
 - 2: Initialize $\hat{\pi}_1$ to any policy in Π
 - 3: **for** $i = 1$ to N **do**
 - 4: Let $\pi_i = \beta_i \pi^* + (1 - \beta_i) \hat{\pi}_i$
 - 5: Sample T -step trajectories using π_i
 - 6: Get dataset $\mathcal{D}_i = \{(s, \pi^*(s))\}$ of visited states by π_i and actions given by expert
 - 7: Aggregate datasets: $\mathcal{D} \leftarrow \mathcal{D} \cup \mathcal{D}_i$
 - 8: Train classifier $\hat{\pi}_{i+1}$ on \mathcal{D}
 - return** best $\hat{\pi}_i$ on validation
-

Inverse Reinforcement Learning

Assuming the expert demonstration is optimal, inverse RL aims to learn the reward function from the expert demonstrations. Consider the reward function has the form of a linear combination of the feature vector components can be a method. From the reward, we can identify the value function. Using conditions of optimal policy, the method aims to find a parameterization of the reward function such that the assumed expert policy is the optimal policy that outperforms other policies.

Apprenticeship Learning

The method aims to learn a policy that has approximately equal performance compared to the expert policy. From the expert trajectories, the procedure for apprenticeship learning can be described as:

Algorithm 2 Apprenticeship Learning via Linear Feature IRL

- 1: Initialize policy π_0
- 2: **for** $i = 1, 2, \dots$ **do**
- 3: Find reward function weights w such that the teacher maximally outperforms all previous controllers:

$$\begin{aligned} & \arg \max_w \max_{\gamma} \gamma \\ & \text{s.t. } w^T \mu(\pi^* | s_0 = s) \geq w^T \mu(\pi | s_0 = s) + \gamma, \forall \pi \in \{\pi_0, \pi_1, \dots, \pi_{i-1}\}, \forall s \\ & \|w\|_2 \leq 1 \end{aligned}$$

- 4: Find optimal policy π_i for current w
 - 5: **if** $\gamma \leq \epsilon/2$ **then return** π_i
-

C. Policy search

Policy search directly parameterize the policy. The method aims to directly find the policy with the highest value function V_{π} , given that the value function is parameterized by θ .

Advantages compared to value-based reinforcement learning:

- Better convergence performance
- Better performance in action spaces that are considered high-dimensional or continuous
- Being able to deal with and learn stochastic policies

Disadvantages:

- Local optima
- Data inefficiency and high variance in policy evaluation

In order to deal with more problems, stochastic policies will be considered in policy search. Stochastic policies can be useful in domains that are adversarial or non-stationary and when the state-representation is not Markov.

Policy objective functions

In episodic environment:

$$J_1(\theta) = V^{\pi_\theta}(s_1) = \mathbb{E}_{\pi_\theta}[v_1]. \quad (16)$$

In continuing environment, the average value of the policy can be used, with $d^{\pi_\theta}(s)$ is the stationary distribution of π_θ :

$$J_{avV}(\theta) = \sum_s d^{\pi_\theta}(s) V^{\pi_\theta}(s). \quad (17)$$

The average reward per time-step can also be a method:

$$J_{avR}(\theta) = \sum_s d^{\pi_\theta}(s) \sum_a \pi_\theta(a|s) R(s|a). \quad (18)$$

For optimizing these objective functions, the method of gradient descent will be focused. Other gradient-free methods sometimes work very well. However, they are usually considered not sample efficient.

Policy gradient

Based on the concepts of gradient descent:

Assuming the policy is parameterized by θ , we ascend the gradient of the policy:

$$\nabla \theta = \alpha \nabla_\theta V(\theta). \quad (19)$$

With α is the step-size, and the policy gradient:

$$\nabla_\theta V(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial V(\theta)}{\partial \theta_1} \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\partial V(\theta)}{\partial \theta_n} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (20)$$

Temporal structure of rewards for policy gradient:

$$\nabla_{\theta} V(\theta) = \nabla_{\theta} \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi(\theta)} [R(\tau)] \approx \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} G_t^{(i)} \cdot \nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a_t^i | s_t^i). \quad (21)$$

The score function in the:

- Discrete action space:

$$\nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a|s) = \phi(s, a) - \mathbb{E}_{a' \sim \pi_{\theta}(a'|s)} [\phi(s, a')]. \quad (22)$$

- Continuous action space:

$$\nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a|s) = \frac{(a - \mu(s))\phi(s)}{\sigma^2}. \quad (23)$$

Using the temporal structure of rewards for policy gradient with Monte-Carlo, we have the REINFORCE algorithm:

Algorithm 1 REINFORCE: Monte-Carlo policy gradient algorithm

- 1: **procedure** REINFORCE(α)
 - 2: Initialize policy parameters θ arbitrarily
 - 3: **for** each episode $\{s_1, a_1, r_2, \dots, s_{T-1}, a_{T-1}, r_T\} \sim \pi_{\theta}$ **do**
 - 4: **for** $t = 1$ to $T - 1$ **do**
 - 5: $\theta \leftarrow \theta + \alpha \cdot G_t \nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a_t | s_t)$
 - return** θ
-

Reducing variance in Policy Gradient

- Causality: With \hat{Q} is the Monte Carlo estimate of Q , the objective function can be modified to reduce variance from prior rewards as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\theta} J(\theta) &\approx \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a_{i,t}, s_{i,t}) \left(\sum_{t'=t}^T \gamma^{t'} r(s_{i,t'}, a_{i,t'}) \right) \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{t=1}^T \left(\nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a_{i,t}, s_{i,t}) \hat{Q}_{i,t} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

- Baselines: Monte-Carlo policy gradient algorithms can have high variance across multiple episodes in the returns $G_t^{(i)}$. To reduce the variance, we can subtract a baseline $b(s)$ as follows. The baseline can be any function that is independent from the action a .

$$\nabla_{\theta} V(\theta) = \nabla_{\theta} \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi_{\theta}} [R(\tau)] = E_{\pi_{\theta}} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{T-1} (G_t - b(s_t)) \nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a_t | s_t) \right]. \quad (25)$$

Vanilla policy gradient

With the baseline function $b(s_t)$ is parameterized with w , the vanilla policy gradient algorithm is as follows:

Algorithm 2 Vanilla Policy Gradient Algorithm

- 1: **procedure** POLICY GRADIENT(α)
- 2: Initialize policy parameters θ and baseline values $b(s)$ for all s , e.g. to 0
- 3: **for** iteration = 1, 2, ... **do**
- 4: Collect a set of m trajectories by executing the current policy π_θ
- 5: **for** each time step t of each trajectory $\tau^{(i)}$ **do**
- 6: Compute the *return* $G_t^{(i)} = \sum_{t'=t}^{T-1} r_{t'}$
- 7: Compute the *advantage estimate* $\hat{A}_t^{(i)} = G_t^{(i)} - b(s_t)$
- 8: Re-fit the baseline to the empirical returns by updating w to minimize

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} \|b(s_t) - G_t^{(i)}\|^2$$

- 9: Update policy parameters θ using the policy gradient estimate \hat{g}

$$\hat{g} = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} \hat{A}_t^{(i)} \nabla_\theta \log \pi_\theta(a_t^{(i)} | s_t^{(i)})$$

with an optimizer like SGD ($\theta \leftarrow \theta + \alpha \cdot \hat{g}$) or Adam
return θ and baseline values $b(s)$

With the baseline method mentioned above, we set the following:

$$\hat{A}_t = \left(G_t^{(i)} - b(s_t) \right). \quad (26)$$

In many cases, the baseline function is set to be the state value function. In this format, \hat{A} will be the advantage function.

D. Fast Reinforcement Learning

1. Bandits & regret

Multi-Armed Bandit

In the multi-armed bandit (MAB) problem, an agent selects an action from a set of actions and receives a reward based on the probability distribution of that action. The agent aims to maximize the cumulative reward. In this setup, there is no delayed rewards and consequences.

The estimated value by Monte Carlo evaluation:

$$\hat{Q}_t(a) = \frac{1}{N_t(a)} \sum_{t=1}^T r_t \mathbf{1}(a_t = a) = \hat{Q}_{t-1}(a) + \frac{1}{N_t(a)} (r_t - \hat{Q}_{t-1}(a)). \quad (27)$$

Optimistic initialization is a simple alternative to ϵ -greedy approaches to increase exploration and escape suboptimal actions. It involves initializing the Q-value estimates for all actions to be larger than the true value. On each step, greedy or ϵ -greedy strategy can be used for selecting the action. Because real rewards are smaller than the original estimates, explored actions will witness a decline in the Q-values, promoting unknown

actions with big Q-value estimations. As a result, every action will be tested at least once.

Regret

Regret is the difference between the expected reward of the optimal action and the expected reward of the action selected by the algorithm over a certain time horizon. When considering regret, the following quantities are also discussed:

- Action-value

$$Q(a) = \mathbb{E}[r|a]. \quad (28)$$

- Optimal value

$$V^* = Q(a^*) = \max_{a \in A} Q(a). \quad (29)$$

- Gap

$$\Delta_a = V^* - Q(a). \quad (30)$$

- Regret

$$l_t = \mathbb{E}[V^* - Q(a_t)]. \quad (31)$$

- Total regret

$$L_t = \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{\tau=1}^t (V^* - Q(a_\tau)) \right] = t \cdot V^* - \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{\tau=1}^t Q(a_\tau) \right]. \quad (32)$$

There are two types of regret bounds:

- Problem independent: Bound according to number of timesteps of the algorithm.
- Problem dependent: Bound according to the number of arm pulling times and gap between the reward of those pulled arms.

The asymptotic lower bound of any algorithm on MAB is:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} L_t \geq \log t \sum_{a|\Delta_a > 0} \frac{\Delta_a}{KL(R^a \parallel R^{a^*})}. \quad (33)$$

The Upper Confidence Bound (UCB) algorithm:

The algorithm estimates an UCB for each and every action value so that with high probability, $Q(a) \leq \hat{Q}_{t(a)} + \hat{U}_t(a)$. Then, we choose actions that maximise the UCB:

$$a_t = \arg \max_{a \in A} \left\{ \hat{Q}_t(a) + \hat{U}_t(a) \right\}. \quad (34)$$

With Hoeffding inequality [4], we get:

$$U_{t(a)} = \sqrt{\frac{-\log p}{2N_t(a)}}. \quad (35)$$

UCB algorithm achieves asymptotic total regret at:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} L_t \leq 8 \log t \sum_{a | \Delta_a > 0} \Delta_a. \quad (36)$$

2. Bayesian bandits to MDPs

Bayesian bandits calculate the probability distribution of rewards in the next following timestep by taking prior knowledge into account, referred to as $p[R]$. This posterior distribution is then utilized to guide the selection of actions.

Assume that the distribution of reward follows a Gaussian distribution, $R^a(r) = N(r; \mu_a, \sigma_a^2)$. We can compute our posterior distribution over μ_a and σ_a^2 with:

$$p[\mu_a, \sigma_a^2 | h_t] \propto p[\mu_a, \sigma_a^2] \prod_{t | a_t = a} N(r_t; \mu_a, \sigma_a^2). \quad (37)$$

To maximize the standard deviation $Q(a)$, we select the action:

$$a_t = \arg \max_{a \in A} \left\{ \mu_a + c \frac{\sigma_a}{\sqrt{N(a)}} \right\}. \quad (38)$$

An approach using probability matching: Choosing an action a based on the likelihood that a is the best action.

$$\pi(a | h_t) = \mathbb{P}(Q(a) > Q(a'), \forall a' \neq a | h_t). \quad (39)$$

Being optimistic in the face of uncertainty means assigning higher probabilities to uncertain actions being the best ones. However, calculating this probability analytically can be challenging. One approach that employs probability matching is called Thompson sampling. This method satisfies the lower bound established by Lai and Robbins [5], and it has proven to be highly effective in practical applications. The process is as follows:

Algorithm 1 Thompson Sampling for Bernoulli MAB using Beta priors

- 1: **for** $i = 1, 2, \dots$ **do**
 - 2: For each arm $k = 1, \dots, N$, independently sample $\theta_k \sim \text{Beta}(S_k + 1, F_k + 1)$
 - 3: Play arm $a_i = \arg \max_k \theta_k$
 - 4: Observe r_i and update S_{a_i}, F_{a_i} accordingly
-

3. Probably approximately correct

PAC, which stands for probably approximately correct, is a theoretical framework that provides problem independent bounds on regret. Regret can result from either numerous small mistakes or infrequent but significant errors. PAC results aim to bound the number of non-small errors. More formally, PAC results guarantee that an algorithm will choose an action a with a value that is ϵ -optimal ($Q(a) \geq Q(a^*) - \epsilon$) with a probability of at least $1 - \delta$, except for a polynomial number of steps. The polynomial is in

terms of the problem parameters such as the number of actions, ϵ , δ , and others. Many PAC algorithms are based on principles like optimism or Thompson sampling.

E. Simulation based search

1. Monte Carlo Tree Search Main principles:

- Using the average returns of random simulations, the true value of a state can be identified.
- These values can be used to iteratively alter the policy in a best-first fashion, allowing us to focus on high-value parts of the search space.

Constructing a partial search tree:

- Current node set as the root.
- Contains nodes corresponding to states s .
- Each node stores statistics: total visit $N(s)$, each pair count $N(s, a)$ and the Monte-Carlo $Q(s, a)$ value estimation.

Variants of Monte Carlo Search Tree:

- Tree policy: Based on the recorded statistics, the tree policy selects actions for nodes in the tree. Variants include greedy and UCB.
- Roll out policy: Implement rules for simulations from the tree's leaf nodes. In the case of AlphaGo, variations include random simulation and the default policy network.

The general Monte Carlo Tree Search is as follows:

Algorithm 1 General MCTS algorithm

```

1: function MCTS( $s_0$ )
2:   Create root node  $v_0$  corresponding to  $s_0$ 
3:   while within computational budget do
4:      $v_k \leftarrow \text{TreePolicy}(v_0)$ 
5:      $\Delta \leftarrow \text{Simulation}(v_k)$ 
6:      $\text{Backprop}(v_k, \Delta)$ 
   return  $\arg \max_a Q(s_0, a)$ 

```

2. Upper Confidence Tree Search

Sometimes, the tree policy can be optimal if use a greedy policy. In order to avoid this, the principle of optimism under uncertainty can be applied to Monte Carlo Search Tree using the Upper Confidence Bound algorithm. With this combination, the model will pick the action with the highest upper confidence bound on the value of the action. The procedure can be done as follows:

Algorithm 2 Upper Confidence Tree policy

```
1: function TREEPOLICY( $v$ )
2:    $v_{next} \leftarrow v$ 
3:   if  $|Children(v_{next})| \neq 0$  then
4:      $a \leftarrow \arg \max_{a \in A} Q(v, a) + \sqrt{\frac{2 \log N(v)}{N(v, a)}}$ 
5:      $v_{next} \leftarrow nextState(v, a)$ 
6:      $v_{next} \leftarrow TreePolicy(v_{next})$ 
   return  $v_{next}$ 
```

IV. DISCUSSION AND LESSON LEARNED

This report, as well as the course, has covered a wide range of topics including value iteration, policy iteration, Q-learning, deep Q-networks, and policy gradients. The course also explored real-world applications and case studies in diverse domains such as robotics, game playing, recommendation systems, and autonomous vehicles. The course also pointed out important research topics and emerging trends in reinforcement learning such as exploration-exploitation trade-offs, model-based, model-free problems, hierarchical reinforcement learning, and multi-agent reinforcement learning. These discussions have fostered critical thinking and provided a platform to discuss and exchange ideas on the future directions of the field.

Throughout the course, the student was able to understand importance of balancing theoretical understanding and practical implementation in reinforcement learning. The information presented has also emphasized the importance of experimentation and empirical evaluation in achieving better performance. The course has highlighted the interdisciplinary nature of reinforcement learning and its connections with other fields such as deep learning, optimization, cognitive science, and control theory. Overall, the course has provided valuable lessons on the theoretical foundations, practical implementation, and real-world applications of reinforcement learning.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE STUDY

In conclusion, the independent study course provided a thorough introduction to the fundamental ideas and techniques in reinforcement learning. It has investigated the ramifications of many algorithms in a variety of disciplines and emphasised their merits in handling complicated decision-making issues. However, several limits and topics for additional research must be acknowledged. One drawback is the difficulty in efficiently managing high-dimensional or continuous state and action spaces. While deep learning algorithms have shown promise in resolving these challenges, more research on sample efficiency and generalisation in such scenarios is required.

The exploration-exploitation trade-off remains a topic requiring further investigation in future research. Striking the right balance between exploring new actions and exploiting established ones is crucial for achieving optimal performance. More sophisticated exploration tactics, such as intrinsic motivation or curiosity-driven exploration, may increase the efficiency and efficacy of reinforcement learning systems.

There is also room to investigate the integration of reinforcement learning with other areas, such as natural language processing or robotics. It would be beneficial to examine the interplay of reinforcement learning with perceptual and planning systems in complicated, real-world circumstances.

While the independent study course laid a solid basis, there are still fascinating prospects for further research and investigation in reinforcement learning, such as tackling scaling challenges, refining exploration tactics, and using RL in varied domains. Continuous improvements in this discipline will help to design more robust and competent learning algorithms.

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